

The Monastery of Vatopaidi, Mount Athos

also known as “The Holy and Great Monastery of Vatopedi”

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Entry tags: Cenobitic Monastery, Christianity, Christian, Greece, Religious Group, Byzantine, Christian Orthodox, Monastery, Greek, Language, Macedonia, Religious Place, Orthodoxy

The Monastery of Vatopaidi is considered as the largest group of buildings in both area and volume on the monastic community of Mount Athos. Hence, from the very first years of its existence it has borne the title of the Megiste ('very great') Monastery of Vatopaidi. In 11th century documents it is encountered as the 'Lavra of Vatopaidi', while in documents of the 14th century is encountered as 'the Great Monastery of Vatopaidi'. Nowadays, the monastery is home to the largest brotherhood amongst the twenty ruling monasteries with well over a hundred monks. The Monastery of Vatopaidi stands on a picturesque stretch of coastline on the gulf of the same name and almost in the center of the north-eastern side of the Athos peninsula. According to the tradition, the monastery was built by the Emperor Constantine the Great (324-337), was subsequently destroyed by Julian the Apostate (361-363) and was re-founded by the Emperor Theodosius the Great (379-395) as a thank-offering to the Blessed Virgin for saving his son Arcadius from certain death by drowning when, as a child, he was in peril in a rough sea near Mount Athos. Arcadius was carried in a miraculous way to the shore, where the sailors found him sleeping near a bramble bush. According to the same tradition, during the 10th century Arab pirates looted and burnt down the monastery, slaughtering the monks and taking away with them to Crete as a prisoner the sacristan, the deacon-monk Sabbas. The biographer of St. Athanasius the Athonite, who lived during the second half of the 10th century mentions three nobles from Adrianople: Athanasius, Nicholas and Antonius that have a direct link with Vatopaidi. The three of them came to Athos with their fortunes, which amounted to 9,000 gold pieces, with the intention of founding a monastery. St. Athanasius, knowing that the monastery of Vatopaidi was in ruins because of the incursion of the pirates, sent them there to restore it. In fact, in a document dated ca. 985, is found the signature of the monk Nicholas as abbot of the monastery. The subsequent growth of the monastery was rapid: in the Typikon of Monomachus (1045), the monastery held the second place in the hierarchy of all the monasteries of Mount Athos, a position which it has retained until the present. It also gained the right to take part in the Synaxis in Karyes in the person of its abbot and four delegates, to keep a yoke of oxen to ensure bread supplies and to have a boat for its needs. At the end of the 12th century, the former prince of Serbia Symeon Nemanja and his son, Savvas, subsequently the first Archbishop and Ethnarch of Serbia, were monks in Vatopaidi. The presence of these two saints lent great prestige both to the monastery and to Mount Athos as a whole. St. Savvas took part in official missions to Constantinople in order to settle issues concerning the Athonite monastic community. It was on his request that the monastery ceded to the Serbian saints the apiary of Chelandari, so that they could build the Serbian monastery of that name. Their presence at Vatopaidi and their benefactions to it were always to remain in the memory of the Serbian people, and all the Serbian princes served as its protectors and benefactors. It was during the time of St. Sabbas that the monastery flourished as never before or after. It had as many as 800 monks, extended its buildings, thanks to the efforts of the two saints, and founded five new chapels on the site. With the founding of the Chelandari Monastery, a kind of spiritual affinity between the two brotherhoods developed. After the unsuccessful attempt of the Emperor Michael VIII Palaeologus (1259-1282) to bring about the reunion of the Eastern and Western Churches at the Council of Lyons (1271), the monastery suffered fresh tribulations. According to the tradition, when the supporters of the union returned from Lyons, they invaded Mount Athos and attempted to force the monks to embrace their views. The refusal of the Vatopaidi brotherhood resulted in the hanging of the Abbot Euthymius and the drowning of 12 monks in the bay of Kalamitsi, as well as the hanging of the Protos of Karyes, St. Cosmas of

Vatopaidi. Shortly afterwards, however, with the aid of the Palaeologues, the monastery recovered. Andronicus II (1282-1328) regarded it as the first and the glorious and provided it with financial support, so that it could return to its former prosperity and state. Throughout its history the monastery has attracted certain major ascetics, most prominent among which were St. Gregory Palamas, the great hesychast theologian, and his teacher St. Nicodemus, St. Joasaph of Meteora, and St. Sabbas, the holy fool, whose life was written by his pupil St. Philotheus, Patriarch of Constantinople. These were followed by St. Macarius Makris, who became the abbot of the Pantocrator Monastery in Constantinople (1431), while during the early years of Turkish rule it sheltered for a while the former Ecumenical Patriarch, Gennadius Scholarius. Around 1500, another Patriarch of Constantinople, St. Niphon, accompanied by his disciples the martyrs Macarius and Joasaph, betook himself to the monastery. It was at this period also that St. Maximus the Greek, the great missionary to the Russians, was a monk at Vatopaidi. According to a testimony of this latter, the monastery at that time followed a semi-coenobitic way of life. The foundation of the Athonite School (the so-called Athonias academy) in 1748 was Vatopaidi's greatest contribution to the interests of the enslaved nation. The building of the school and its operation were fully undertaken by the monastery, during a period when it faced major economic problems because of the crippling taxation imposed by the Turkish authorities. The Athonite School was the biggest Greek school in the Greek world under Turkish occupation, reaching ca. 200 students. Its first director was the hierodeacon Neofytos Kafsokalyvitis. After the resignation of Neofytos, Evgenios Voulgaris became the director, while the teachers included the hierodeacons Kyprianos Kyprios, afterwards Patriarch of Alexandria (1766-1783), Nikolaos Tzertzoulis and Panayotis Palamas. Among the more famous of the school's pupils were St. Cosmas of Aetolia, Righas Ferraios, the scholar and writer Sergios Makraios, the teacher Iosipos Misiodax, and the theologian Athanasios of Paros. St. Nicodemus the Athonite and Adamantios Koraes were among those who toiled to ensure its smooth operation. Vatopaidi has a history of supporting various causes and has continued in more modern times to generously provide alms. In 1880, the monastery donated 3,700 pounds for the building of the Great School of the Nation and in 1908 offered 5,000 pounds to the Theological School of Chalki. A crucial point in the monastery's recent history was its re-manning in 1987 by a group of monks led by the elder Joseph Spilaiotis, from Agiou Pavlou Monastery's Nea Skete. Moreover, following a resolution on the part of the fathers of the monastery and with a sigillium from the late Ecumenical Patriarch, Demetrius I, in 1989 the monastery returned, after the elapse of centuries, to the coenobitic system. Archimandrite Ephraim was elected as first Abbot, and his enthronement took place on the Second Sunday after Easter (29 April) 1990.

Date Range: 950 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Mount Athos, Greece

Region tags: Greece

The Holy and Great Monastery of Vatopedi in Mount Athos, Greece

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Αρκάδιος Ιεροδιάκονος Βατοπαιδινός, Ιστορία της Ιεράς Μεγίστης Μονής Βατοπαιδίου, 2022

- Source 2: The monastery of Vatopedi. History and Art. Gounaridis Paris (ed.), Athens 1999
- Source 3: Pavlikianov Cyril, The Athonite Monastery of Vatopedi from 1462 to 1707, Sofia 2008

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.vatopedi.gr/>
- Source 1 Description: The official website of the Monastery
- Source 2 URL: <https://proskynitaria2.mountathos.org/TrapezaVatopaidiou-3D/>
- Source 2 Description: 3D model of the refectory of the Vatopaidi monastery
- Source 3 URL: <https://proskynitaria2.mountathos.org/maximos/>
- Source 3 Description: St. Maximus the Greek-multimedia application
- Source 1 URL: <https://proskynitaria2.mountathos.org/athonikesprosopikotites/>
- Source 1 Description: Athonite Prosopography
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.monastiria.gr/mount-athos-vatopedi-monastery/?lang=en>
- Source 2 Description: The Vatopaidi Monastery
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.vatopedi.com/en/vatopedi-monastery>
- Source 3 Description: Mount Athos & Holy Great Monastery of Vatopedi

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1983-2021

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Works at the monastery of Vatopaidi by the Centre of Preservation of Athonite Heritage

Reference: Centre for the Preservation of the Athonite Heritage. "Works at the Vatopaidi Monastery", 2024. <https://www.kedak.gr/erga/syntelesthen-ergo/iera-moni-vatopediou/>.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: a large square

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
– As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery commemorates Saints Athanasius, Nicholas, and Anthony, the tenth century founders of Vatopaidi Monastery.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Notes: According to Athonite tradition, the monastery was built by the Emperor Constantine the Great, was subsequently destroyed by Julian the Apostate (361-363) and was re-founded by the Emperor Theodosius the Great (379-395) as a thank-offering to the Blessed Virgin for saving his son Arcadius from certain death by drowning when, as a child, he was in peril in a rough sea near Mount Athos. Arcadius was carried in a miraculous manner to the shore, where the sailors found him sleeping near a bramble bush.

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: According to the tradition the monastery was re-founded by the Emperor Theodosius the Great (379-395) as a thank-offering to the Blessed Virgin for saving his son Arcadius from certain death by drowning when, as a child, he was in peril in a rough sea near Mount Athos. Arcadius was carried in a miraculous manner to the shore, where the sailors found him sleeping near a bramble bush. For this reason the monastery was called Vatopaidi: a child in a bramble bush.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: According to the tradition the monastery was re-founded by the Emperor Theodosius the Great (379-395) as a thank-offering to the Blessed Virgin for saving his son Arcadius from certain death by drowning when, as a child, he was in peril in a rough sea near Mount Athos. Arcadius was carried in a miraculous manner to the shore, where the sailors found him sleeping near a bramble bush. For this reason the monastery was called Vatopaidi: a child in a bramble bush.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Reference: Liakos, Dimitrios. "The Byzantine Bell-tower in Vatopedi Monastery on Mount Athos (1427)". *JÖB* 65 (2015): 153–68.

Reference: Mamaloukos, Stavros. "The Buildings of Vatopedi and Their Patrons". In *Mount Athos and Byzantine Monasticism. Papers from the Twenty-eighth Spring Symposium of Byzantine Studies*, University of Birmingham, 113–26. Birmingham: Routledge, 1996.

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 85

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 400

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 29

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 350

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Clay

– Field doesn't know

↳ Plaster

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: metal, marble

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Reference: Sofragiu , Petru. "The Mural Paintings of the Exonarthex of Vatopedi Monastery's Katholikon". *European Journal of Science and Theology* 8, no. 4 (2012): 233–46.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: abstract & floral decoration.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Not exactly. However, the founders of the Vatopedi Monastery are buried in a tomb at the southern end of the katholikon (the main Church). These are the Saints Athanasios, Nikolaos and Antonios. Recent archeological research has proven that their tomb was built at the same time with the katholikon.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 40

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: Since the vast majority of the brotherhood at the monastery consists of monks of Cypriot origin, many Cypriots consider a visit at the Vatopaidi Monastery as a short of pilgrimage. However, this is not mandatory.

Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Field doesn't know

Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

– specify: monthly

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 90

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Notes: In fact yes. Monks in Mount Athos abstain from eating meat. There are nevertheless certain festive periods during which monks also abstain from oil. In general, food in Mt. Athos (and consequently in Vatopaidi Monastery) consists of vegetables, fruits, and cereals.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: All monks in Mount Athos, religious specialists included, are males. In fact, there is a prohibition regarding female presence throughout Mount Athos.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: In general, most of the monks are of Greek or Cypriot origin. There are also monks from the Balkan peninsula countries (Romania, Serbia etc) as well as some Russians.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities and the Centre for the Preservation of the Athonite Heritage are responsible for the maintenance, as well as the excavations in the Vatopaidi monastery.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned

with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: It should be mentioned that in September of 2008, the monastery was implicated in an alleged real estate scandal, accused of trading low-value land for high-value state property in a deal with the government of Prime Minister Kostas Karamanlis. In the ensuing court case, all of the accused were ultimately acquitted and it was decided that there was no financial damage to the public treasury.

Reference: Laiou , Angeliki. "Economic Activities of Vatopedi in the Fourteenth Century". *Αθωνικά Σύμμεικτα* 7 (1999): 55-72.

Reference: Lefort , Jaques. "La Fortune Foncière De Vatopédi Hors De L'athos Avant La Fin Du Xiiiè Siècle". *Αθωνικά Σύμμεικτα* 7 (1999): 43-54.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Yes

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Monastery of Vatopaidi, Mount Athos, Speake, Graham, and Kallistos Ware, eds.. Mount Athos. Edited by Graham Speake and Kallistos Ware. Peter Lang UK, 2012.

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Reference: The Monastery of Vatopaidi, Mount Athos, Androutis , Paschalis. "Quelques Réflexions À Propos De L'étoffe Luxueuse Du Despote De Thessalonique Andronic Paléologue, Jadis Conservée Au Monastère Athonite De Vatopédi". Cahiers Balkaniques 48 (2021): 67-88. <https://doi.org/10.4000/ceb.18405>.

Reference: The Monastery of Vatopaidi, Mount Athos, Dumont , Pierre. "La Conférence Interorthodoxe De Vatopédi". Irénikon 8, no. 2 (1931): 97-107.

Reference: The Monastery of Vatopaidi, Mount Athos, Gómez Raúl , Estangüi , and Christophe Giros. "L'apport Des Actes De Vatopédi À L'étude De L'histoire De La Fin De L'empire Byzantin". In Comptes-

rendus Des Séances De L'académie Des Inscriptions Et Belles-lettres, 71-87. Paris: Editions de l'Academie, 2020.

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Reference: Yes, Laiou , Angeliki. "Economic Activities of Vatopedi in the Fourteenth Century". *Αθωνικά Σύμμεικτα* 7 (1999): 55-72.

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